

A stabilizing predictive controller with implicit feedforward compensation for stable and time-delayed systems

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Abstract

Predictive controllers stand out as a realizable solution concerning disturbance rejection in comparison to classical feedforward compensators. However, stability attributes are still scarce in studies of predictive model controllers with implicit disturbance compensation. Therefore, this paper proposes a nominal stable model predictive control with implicit feedforward action for stable and time-delayed systems. The control formulation is presented based on the state-space model representation, considering the control inputs and measured disturbances increments. The control law results in a one-layer optimization problem providing optimal input moves that lead the process output to the desired reference rejecting the measured disturbances in a stable closed-loop response. The nominal stability properties are guaranteed by proving that the control cost function is a Lyapunov function. A solar collector field is used as a case study to show the disturbance rejection and overall performance characteristics of the proposed control strategy. Simulation results demonstrate the advantages and progress of the novel control algorithm and its capabilities to circumvent common issues that arise from disturbance rejection with classical feedforward

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structures.

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1. Introduction

The most widespread control objective is maintaining the process outputs in the desired reference set. However, this simple concept faces several issues, such as disturbance effects, that may compromise the control objective and deviate the process output from the defined setpoint. Control strategies that minimize the influence of the disturbance in the control loop are called feedforward controllers or feedforward compensators. This control method is the most common solution in literature to compensate for the effects of measured disturbances before they affect the process output. The classical feedforward compensator is expressed based on the fundamental concept to eliminate the disturbance effects by dividing the dynamics relating to the measured disturbance and the process output by the dynamics relating to the control action and the process output [1]. Nevertheless, this conceptual formulation is hard to implement when there are causality problems, and complicated dynamic structures that can even lead to an unstable closed-loop controller [2, 3].

A successful control algorithm capable of dealing with disturbance effects is the Model Predictive Controller (MPC) [4]. MPC can compensate for disturbance interference in the process output by adopting an internal model that relates the dynamics of the measured disturbances to the process outputs. In this case, the optimization problem can be formulated based on the minimization of the predicted output error using the internal model with the implicit feedforward dynamics. This strategy can face causality, nonlinear and unstable dynamics issues and incorporate inputs and outputs restrictions into the control optimization problem. Most of the MPC strategies focus on minimizing future output error by tuning the controller parameters, such as output prediction horizon, control horizon, weighting matrices, and equality and inequality

constraints. However, the MPC with an implicit feedforward action must consider an appropriate control design since a wrong choice of the controller tuning associated with the receding horizon control structure can cause performance deterioration and, in some cases, an unstable closed-loop response [3, 5, 6]. Research on the stability properties of MPC strategies is a vast and variate field. A broadly studied subject for stable predictive control methods is the state-feedback framework. The central idea of this set of strategies is to demonstrate that the optimal cost function can be treated as a Lyapunov function by employing contracting constraints to the system states along prediction horizons and, thus, the stability properties can be accounted for by the control law. This approach can consider model uncertainties, any model dynamics, and also bounded disturbances. Concerning the state-contracting procedure, the work of Khotare et al. [7] presents one of the first robustly stable MPC approaches. Although stability can be achieved for stable, unstable, integrating, and bounded disturbed systems, there are severe concerns about feasibility due to the application of hard constraints, which led to various studies to improve this concept (see Refs. [8, 9, 10, 11]). Recently, Shokrollahi and Shamaghdari [5] proposed a robustly stable infinite horizon controller for nonlinear systems subjected to norm-bounded disturbances. The proposed controller is formulated as a Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI) optimization problem to minimize the upper bound of an infinite horizon objective function, thus, making progress from previous works concerning implementation on nonlinear systems (see Refs. [12, 13, 14]). Even though state-feedback approaches have been enhanced over the years, this control technique has the shortcoming of high computational processing time due to the resulting optimization problem and faces stability and feasibility issues regarding the rigorous condition of states convergence toward the equilibrium point (typically the origin), which reduces the controller domain of attraction [15].

The employment of hard constraints at the end of the control horizon may reduce the domain of attraction and cause infeasibility issues, mainly when considering practical applications [16]. Hence, several studies have been carried

out to increase the domain of attraction of stable predictive controllers. For instance, in Limon et al. [17], the authors have proposed a finite horizon MPC for reference tracking case wherein artificial steady states and input variables are used as decision variables of the optimization problem. In that solution, an extended stabilizing terminal condition is imposed as a tracking error penalty and a terminal constraint for the state and the artificial variables in the cost function. In the mentioned work, the authors have demonstrated that a large domain of attraction and a control law near the optimal can be achieved by choosing a large weight for the tracking error term. This solution has been successfully implemented in subsequent works ([18, 19, 20]).

On the other hand, inspired by the primordial work of Rawlings and Muske [21], Rodrigues and Odloak [22] presented an Infinity Horizon MPC (IH MPC) control extension, including both the regulatory and the reference tracking cases in a single layer for systems with stable poles. The extended controller increases the domain of attraction by including slack variables that smooth the terminal constraints of the IH MPC, and hence ensuring the feasibility of the optimization problem. The solution presented by Rodrigues and Odloak [22] led to the development of diverse infinite horizon predictive controllers, mainly focused on practical applications, including formulations for unstable, single, and multiple integrator poles and time-delayed processes. Nonetheless, the previously mentioned IH MPC strategies do not include measured disturbances dynamics, and, to the best of our knowledge, this notion is still lacking in the literature. The inclusion of the disturbance model requires additional states that need to be accounted for in the control problem formulation aiming to guarantee the nominal stability properties. Moreover, the benefits of including the FF action in the predictive strategies overcome the significant issues regarding external FF control strategies that could be added to the already proposed IH MPC frameworks, such as non-invertible dynamics and input constraints. Table 1 summarizes the significant advances related to slacked terminal constraints IH MPC based on original works of Rawlings and Muske [21] for nominal cases and Badgwell [23] for multi-plant cases.

Table 1: Stable IHMPC controllers based on feasible solution with slacked terminal constraints

Theoretical Contribution	System	Internal Controller Model	Measured Disturbance	Related works
Rawlings and Muske (1993) [21]	Stable	Nominal	-	
Badgwell (1997) [23]	Stable	Multi-plant	-	
Rodrigues and Odloak (2003) [22]	Stable	Nominal	-	Pataro et al. (2020) [24], Pataro et al. (2019a) [25]
Odloak (2004) [26]	Stable	Multi-plant	-	Brugnolli et al. (2019) [27], Martin et al. (2019) [28] Álvarez and Odloak (2012) [29], González et al. (2011) [30]
Carrapiço and Odloak (2005) [31]	Stable and integrating	Nominal	-	Silva et al. (2020) [32]
González et al. (2006) [33]	Stable and integrating	Multi-plant	-	Delou et al. (2021) [34], Álvarez and Odloak (2010) [35], González et al. (2009) [36]
González and Odloak (2011) [37]	Stable and time-delay	Multi-plant	-	Nogueira et al. (2020) [38], Martins et al. (2014) [39]
Santoro (2011) [40]	Integrating and time delay	Multi-plant	-	Martins et al. (2013)[41]
Martins and Odloak (2016) [15]	Stable, integrating, unstable	Multi-plant	-	Sencio and Odloak (2018) [42]
Costa (2017) [43]	Multiple integrating	Nominal	-	Costa et al. (2017) [44]
Pataro et al. (2019b) [45]	Multiple integrating	Multi-plant	-	
This work	Stable, time delay	Nominal	×	-

Based on the foregoing survey, it is notable that the design and study of
90 the predictive control framework with implicit feedforward action and stability
assurance have not yet been handled in feasible IHMPC formulations. Therefore,
to fill in these remaining gaps, the present work proposes a closed-loop nominally
stable infinite horizon model predictive control with implicit feedforward action
(IHMPCFF) for stable and time-delayed systems. Intending to demonstrate
95 the practical applicability of the proposed control strategy and investigate its
disturbance rejection features, the IHMPCFF is employed to control a flat-plate
solar collector field, which is characterized as a time-delayed and constantly
disturbed system. In this context, it is worth stressing that the rejection of
disturbances is a crucial issue that must be considered in the control design for
100 solar collector field systems, mainly because the non-manipulable variables are
the ones that most interfere in the process output, but on the other hand, they
can be easily measured nowadays, which motivates the study of feedforward
compensators [46, 47, 48, 49]. The significant contributions of the present work
are depicted as follows:

- 105 (i) the novel IHMPCFF strategy makes progress over IHMPC with soften-
ing terminal constraints, as described in Table 1, by adopting implicit
disturbances rejection and maintaining stability and feasibility properties
regarding well-established notions on recursive viability and asymptoti-
cally decreasing of the cost function [22];
- 110 (ii) the present work contributes to the study of the stable IHMPC concerning
its ability to compensate for the measured disturbances, comparing the
IHMPCFF with a classic IHMPC with an external feedforward action.
The presented analysis is based on perfect disturbances elimination, non-
causality issues, and inputs saturation restriction following the analysis
115 presented in Ref. [3];
- (iii) this work presents the application of a stabilizing MPC strategy in solar
thermal energy facilities, which is a still missing contribution in the re-
newable energy research field [50, 51, 52, 53, 54]. The proposed control

strategy is tested in a validated model of a real solar thermal plant located at CIESOL center (University of Almería, Spain). The nonlinear system is studied considering the linearization point of the plant, adaptive linear model parameters calculation, controller sampling time, and control horizon, wherein all these features are related to the IHMPCFF applicability.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 details the IHMPCFF model formulation and presents the proof of the stability properties. In Section 3 the proposed control strategy is investigated regarding its capabilities of disturbance rejection. Section 4 depicts the solar collector field studies concerning the employment of the IHMPCFF strategy in practical scenarios. Lastly, the conclusions and discussions are presented in Section 5.

2. The IHMPCFF formulation

The proposed IHMPCFF controller is herein formulated. First, a model extension for a stable and time-delayed system with measured disturbances is presented based on the step response approach. Then, the control problem is formulated considering the Lyapunov stability properties of the closed-loop system.

2.1. Model construction

In this section, the IHMPCFF is expressed based on previous works presented by Rodrigues and Odloak [22] and Santoro [40]. The formulation is expressed in space-state fashion as an Output Prediction Oriented Model (OPOM), developed from the analytical form of the step response procedure. This model is based on a linear formulation originated from transfer function notions, which can accurately represent the system dynamics around the chosen operating point.

Consider a Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) transfer function $G_{i,j}(s)$ constituted by the pair $(y_i$ output, u_j input) and $Gd_{i,g}(s)$ constituted by the

pair (y_i output, d_g measured disturbance). The transfer function in the Laplace domain, s , is presented as:

$$\begin{aligned} G_{i,j}(s) &= \frac{y_i(s)}{u_j(s)} = \frac{b_{i,j,0} + b_{i,j,1}s + \dots + b_{i,j,nb}}{(s - r_{i,j,0}^{st}) \dots (s - r_{i,j,na}^{st})} e^{-\gamma_{i,j}s} \\ Gd_{i,g}(s) &= \frac{y_i(s)}{d_g(s)} = \frac{b_{i,g,0} + b_{i,g,1}s + \dots + b_{i,g,np}}{(s - r_{i,g,0}^{std}) \dots (s - r_{i,g,nc}^{std})} e^{-\phi_{i,g}s} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

in which $na > nb$ and $nc > np$, being na and nc the number of poles and nb and np the number of zeros of the transfer function $G_{i,j}(s)$ and $Gd_{i,g}(s)$, respectively. Moreover, $r_{i,j}^{st}$ and $r_{i,g}^{std}$ are the stable poles of the systems related to the input and measured disturbances, respectively. Also, $\gamma_{i,j}$ and $\phi_{i,g}$ are the process delays of $G_{i,j}(s)$ and $Gd_{i,g}(s)$, respectively. Applying a step response procedure for both dynamics in discrete time with a sampling time T_s and using the partial fraction method, the step response function can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{i,j}(kT_s) &= h_{i,j}^{0,u} + \sum_{l=1}^{na} h_{i,j,l}^u e^{r_{i,j,l}^{st}(kT_s - \gamma_{i,j})} \\ S_{i,g}(kT_s) &= h_{i,g}^{0,d} + \sum_{l=1}^{nc} h_{i,g,l}^d e^{r_{i,g,l}^{std}(kT_s - \phi_{i,g})} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Based on that, and following Martins and Odloak [15], from Eq. (2), the equivalent state-space model for the incremental form of the inputs and measured disturbances is expressed in Eqs. (3) and (4).

For this representation, ny , nu , and nd are the number of inputs, outputs and disturbances, respectively. In addition, α_{max} is the maximum inputs delay, and β_{max} is the maximum disturbance delay. Also, consider:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x} &\in \mathbb{C}^{nx}, \quad \mathbf{x}^s \in \mathbb{R}^{ny}, \quad \mathbf{x}^{st} \in \mathbb{C}^{nst}, \quad \mathbf{x}^d \in \mathbb{C}^{ndst}, \quad \Delta \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^{nu}, \\ \mathbf{z}_1 \dots \mathbf{z}_{\alpha_{max}} &\in \mathbb{R}^{\alpha_{max}}, \quad \mathbf{z}_1 \dots \mathbf{z}_{\beta_{max}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\beta_{max}}, \quad \mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{ny}, \\ nst &= ny \cdot nu \cdot \max(na), \quad ndst = ny \cdot nd \cdot \max(nc), \quad nx = 2 \cdot ny + nst + ndst, \end{aligned}$$

For constructing matrices \mathbf{F} , Ψ , \mathbf{B}_l^s and \mathbf{B}_l^{st} , the procedure is borrowed from Martins and Odloak (2016) [15], and the algorithm is replicated for the disturbance states regarding the matrices \mathbf{F}^d , Ψ^d , \mathbf{B}_l^s and \mathbf{B}_l^{st} .

$$\mathbf{y}(k) = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{ny} & \Psi & \Psi^d & \mathbf{0} & \dots & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}}_{\mathbf{C}} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}^s(k) \\ \mathbf{x}^{st}(k) \\ \mathbf{x}^d(k) \\ \mathbf{z}_1(k) \\ \mathbf{z}_2(k) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{z}_{\alpha_{max}}(k) \\ \mathbf{z}_1^d(k) \\ \mathbf{z}_2^d(k) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{z}_{\beta_{max}}^d(k) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

The model states $\mathbf{x}^s(k)$ are related to the incremental form of the inputs and disturbances (artificial integrating states), $\mathbf{x}^{st}(k)$ are the states related to the stable poles of the system regarding the control inputs, and $\mathbf{x}^d(k)$ are the states related to the stable poles of the system regarding the disturbances. States $\mathbf{z}_l(k)$ are related to the past delayed moves of the inputs, and $\mathbf{z}_p^d(k)$ are the past delayed moves related to the disturbances.

2.2. IHMPCFF control formulation

Based on the proposed model for systems with measured disturbances and time delays, the IHMPCFF optimization problem is formulated based on the following objective function:

$$J_k = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \|\mathbf{y}(k+j|k) - \mathbf{y}_{sp} - \boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k}\|_{\mathbf{Q}_y}^2 + \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} \|\Delta \mathbf{u}(k+j|k)\|_{\mathbf{R}}^2 + \|\boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k}\|_{\mathbf{S}_y}^2 \quad (5)$$

in which $\mathbf{y}(k+j|k)$ is the predicted output vector, \mathbf{y}_{sp} the future references vector, $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k} \in \mathbb{R}^{ny}$ is the vector of slack variables, $\mathbf{Q}_y \in \mathbb{R}^{ny \times ny}$ is the positive definite weighting matrix for the system outputs, $\Delta \mathbf{u}(k+j|k)$ is the incremental inputs, $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{nu \times nu}$ is positive definite weighting matrix for the

170 system inputs, $\mathbf{S}_y \in \mathbb{R}^{ny \times ny}$ is the positive definite weighting matrices slack
variable $\boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k}$ and m is the control horizon.

The proposed objective function is not yet limited due the presence of artificial integrating states originated from the proposed form of the incremental inputs. Moreover, for the expressed IHMPC with implicit feedforward action, it
175 is assumed that both the control inputs and disturbances are constant beyond the control horizon, that is $\Delta \mathbf{u}(k+j|k) = \mathbf{0}$ and $\Delta \mathbf{d}(k+j|k) = \mathbf{0}$ for $j \geq m$.

Remark 1. *In MPC frameworks, the future input values are the decision variables, which are assumed to be known to the controller. However, the future measured disturbances are unknown. Therefore, a common and plausible practice constantly employed in predictive control algorithms, mainly when the disturbance dynamic is expressed as a step form, is to assume that the measured disturbances will remain constant at the last available measurement [6, 55].*
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Therefore, to limit the cost function, it is proposed a slacked terminal equality constraint for the artificial integrating states $\mathbf{x}^s(k)$, which is:

$$\underbrace{\mathbf{I}_{ny} \mathbf{x}^s(k|k) + \sum_{l=0}^{m+\alpha_{max}-1} \mathbf{B}_l^s \Delta \mathbf{u}(k-l) + \sum_{l=0}^{m+\beta_{max}-1} \mathbf{B}_d^s \Delta \mathbf{d}(k-l) - \mathbf{y}_{sp} - \boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k}}_{\mathbf{x}^s(k+m+w_{max}|k)} = \mathbf{0} \quad (6)$$

185 wherein the maximum delay is defined as $w_{max} = \max(\alpha, \beta)$.

Hence, following the terminal constraint in Eq. (6) the optimization problem is reduced to:

$$J_k = \sum_{j=1}^{m+w_{max}} \|\mathbf{y}(k+j|k) - \mathbf{y}_{sp} - \boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k}\|_{\mathbf{Q}_y}^2 + \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} \|\Delta \mathbf{u}(k+j|k)\|_{\mathbf{R}}^2 \quad (7)$$

$$+ \|\mathbf{x}^{st}(k+m+w_{max}|k)\|_{\overline{\mathbf{Q}}}^2 + \|\mathbf{x}^d(k+m+w_{max}|k)\|_{\overline{\mathbf{Q}}_d}^2 + \|\boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k}\|_{\mathbf{S}_y}^2$$

in which the terminal weighting matrices $\overline{\mathbf{Q}}$ and $\overline{\mathbf{Q}}_d$ are the solution of the Lyapunov equation:

$$\begin{aligned}\overline{\mathbf{Q}} &= \mathbf{F}^\top \boldsymbol{\Psi}^\top \mathbf{Q}_y \mathbf{F} \boldsymbol{\Psi} + \mathbf{F}^\top \overline{\mathbf{Q}} \mathbf{F} \\ \overline{\mathbf{Q}}_d &= \mathbf{F}^{d^\top} \boldsymbol{\Psi}^{d^\top} \mathbf{Q}_y \mathbf{F}^d \boldsymbol{\Psi}^d + \mathbf{F}^{d^\top} \overline{\mathbf{Q}}_d \mathbf{F}^d\end{aligned}$$

190 Therefore, the nominal stabilizing control law is obtained from the solution of the following optimization problem:

Problem 1:

$$\min_{\Delta \mathbf{u}_k, \delta_{y,k}} J_k,$$

subjected to Eq. (6) and:

$$U = \begin{cases} \Delta \mathbf{u}_{\min} \leq \Delta \mathbf{u}(k+j|k) \leq \Delta \mathbf{u}_{\max}, \\ \Delta \mathbf{u}(k+j|k) = 0, j \geq m, \\ \mathbf{u}_{\min} \leq \mathbf{u}(k+j|k) \leq \mathbf{u}_{\max}, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Remark 2. *The proposed optimization problem presents slack variables for always providing a feasible solution. In order to guarantee that the control inputs will lead the system outputs to the desired reference without offset, the weighting matrix \mathbf{S}_y is defined sufficiently larger than \mathbf{Q}_y and \mathbf{R} . Nevertheless, suppose the slacks variables are not zeroed at the end of the control horizon. In that case, the optimization problem will provide control inputs that will lead the system's outputs to the minimum distance to the outputs reference.*

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200 The nominal stability guarantee of the IHMPCFF controller is achieved by the proof of the following **Theorem**:

Theorem 2.1. *Given a system with stable poles, time-delayed, measured disturbances in time instant k , and that the disturbances are constant along and beyond the control horizon. Assume that at time step k there is a feasible solution of the **Problem 1**. If the desired steady-state is possible, then the solution to **Problem 1** at the subsequent time steps leads to the process outputs asymptotically to the desired reference. Otherwise, in case the reference is not reachable, the process outputs will converge to the closest equilibrium point with the lowest distance from the reference.*

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210 *Proof.* The **Theorem** proof follows the same principles presented by Rawlings
and Muske [21] and employed by Rodrigues and Odloak [22], which considers
the recursive viability of the solution and the asymptotical convergence of the
cost function. First, for the recursive viability, it must be shown that the so-
lution inherited from the instant k is a plausible solution for the instant $k + 1$.
215 Therefore, consider that at k , the following optimal solution is obtained:

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}_k^* = [\Delta \mathbf{u}^*(k|k)^\top \Delta \mathbf{u}^*(k+1|k)^\top \cdots \Delta \mathbf{u}^*(k+m-1|k)^\top]^\top,$$

$$\delta_{y,k}^*,$$

which produces the minimum cost value J_k^* . The control action $\Delta \mathbf{u}^*(k|k)$ is
implemented at the system and using the receding horizon concept, at sampling
instant $k + 1$, **Problem 1** is solved again. Since the control scenario is given as
nominal, the next solution at $k + 1$ can be the inhaled solution of k , as follows:

$$\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+1} = [\Delta \mathbf{u}^*(k+1|k)^\top \Delta \mathbf{u}^*(k+2|k)^\top \cdots \mathbf{0}^\top]^\top,$$

$$\tilde{\delta}_{y,k+1} = \delta_{y,k}^*,$$

It is easy to follow that $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+1}$ can satisfy the optimization problem restric-
tion regarding Eq. (8) since the only term different from $\Delta \mathbf{u}_k^*$ is $\mathbf{0}$, which is
included in all input constraint sets. Hence, only the terminal constraint needs
to be analyzed. Consider the terminal constraint Eq. (6) at $k + 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}^s(k+m+w_{max}+1|k+1) - \mathbf{y}_{sp} - \delta_{y,k+1} &= \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{I}_{ny} \mathbf{x}^s(k|k) + \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^m \mathbf{B}_l^s \Delta \mathbf{u}_{k+1} + \sum_{l=m+1}^{m+\alpha_{max}} \mathbf{B}_l^s \Delta \mathbf{u}(k-l) + \sum_{l=0}^{m+\beta_{max}} \mathbf{B} \mathbf{d}_l^s \Delta \mathbf{d}(k-l)}_{\mathbf{x}^s(k+m+w_{max}+1|k+1) = \mathbf{x}^s(k+m+w_{max}+1|k)} - \mathbf{y}_{sp} - \delta_{y,k+1} &= \mathbf{0} \end{aligned}$$

220 Note that, as the nominal case is assumed, that is, the internal model of
the IHMPC accurately describes the dynamics of the model, and considering
the hypothesis of knowing the disturbances that affect the process along the

control horizon, the premise of knowing the future states holds, thus, $\mathbf{x}^s(k + m + w_{max} + 1|k + 1) = \mathbf{x}^s(k + m + w_{max} + 1|k)$ can be imposed. Therefore, the state $\mathbf{x}^s(k + m + w_{max} + 1|k)$ can be computed using the optimal in-hered solution obtained at the instant k , which is:

$$\underbrace{\mathbf{I}_{ny}\mathbf{x}^s(k|k) + \sum_{l=0}^m \mathbf{B}_l^s \Delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+1} + \sum_{l=m+1}^{m+\alpha_{max}} \mathbf{B}_l^s \Delta \mathbf{u}(k-l) + \sum_{l=0}^{m+\beta_{max}} \mathbf{B}d_l^s \Delta \mathbf{d}(k-l) - \mathbf{y}_{sp} - \tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}_{y,k+1}}_{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}^s(k+m+w_{max}+1|k)} = \mathbf{0} \quad (9)$$

By comparing Eqs. (6) and (9), it can be noted that the only difference appears from the state prediction performed from one sampling time ahead, $k + 1$, which considers $\Delta \mathbf{u}(k + m + \alpha_{max})$ and $\Delta \mathbf{d}(k + m + \beta_{max})$. However, as stated before in **Remark 1**, both terms are assumed to be zero. Therefore, the in-hered solution for the instant $k + 1$ results the same terminal constraint already solved at instant k :

$$\underbrace{\mathbf{I}_{ny}\mathbf{x}^s(k|k) + \sum_{l=0}^m \mathbf{B}_l^s \Delta \mathbf{u}_k^* + \sum_{l=m+1}^{m+\alpha_{max}-1} \mathbf{B}_l^s \Delta \mathbf{u}(k-l) + \sum_{l=0}^{m+\beta_{max}-1} \mathbf{B}d_l^s \Delta \mathbf{d}(k-l) - \mathbf{y}_{sp} - \boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k}^*}_{\text{Eq. (6)}} = \mathbf{0} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) completes the proof for the recursive viability step. The next step is to demonstrate that the cost function will be asymptotically decreasing. Subsequently, since the in-hered solution $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+1}$ and $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}_{y,k+1}$ are plausible solutions, let \tilde{J}_{k+1} be the associated cost at $k + 1$ calculated by the in-hered solution in k . It is easy to note that the only difference in the cost value at $k + 1$ and at k is the first term associated to the implemented control action $\Delta \mathbf{u}^*(k|k)$. Hence, the cost function difference is depicted as:

$$J_k^* - \tilde{J}_{k+1} = \|\mathbf{y}(k|k) - \mathbf{y}_{sp}(k) - \boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k}^*\|_{\mathbf{Q}_y}^2 + \|\Delta \mathbf{u}(k|k)\|_{\mathbf{R}}^2 \quad (11)$$

Since \mathbf{Q}_y and \mathbf{R} are positive semi-definite matrices, it can be observed that $J_k^* \geq \tilde{J}_{k+1}$. Consequently, $\Delta \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{k+1}$ and $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\delta}}_{y,k+1}$ are a feasible solution for the **Problem 1** at $k + 1$, which correspond to $J_k^* \geq \tilde{J}_{k+1} \geq J_{k+1}^*$.

As $J_k^* \geq J_{k+1}^*$, the same procedure is replicated for the subsequent time instants $(k+j)$. By following the presented steps, it can be seen that the cost function J_k is employed as a Lyapunov function and hence does satisfy the Lyapunov stability of the closed-loop system. It is noteworthy to note that if the reference is not reachable, then the cost function converges to a penalized minimum related to the offset error associated with the slack variable $(\mathbf{y}(\infty) - \mathbf{y}_{sp}(\infty) = \boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k}^*)$, that is:

$$J_\infty^* = \left\| \boldsymbol{\delta}_{y,k}^* \right\|_{\mathbf{S}_y}^2$$

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□

3. Disturbance rejection analysis

In this section, the study of the IHMPCFF disturbance rejections based on three main functionalities is presented, namely: tuning condition for perfect elimination of the disturbance dynamic, non-causal issues, and input constraints. The results of Pawlowski et al. [3] served as the basis for the following system examples. The analysis is performed by comparing the classical IHMPC ([22]) plus a classical external feedforward compensator, herein stated as IHMPC+FF, with the previous proposed strategy IHMPCFF in which an implicit feedforward action is included.

3.1. Tuning condition for IHMPCFF disturbance rejection

For the first scenario, consider an input non-restricted optimization problem for the IHMPCFF controller, wherein only the terminal constraint is imposed. In addition, for direct and simpler analysis purposes, consider that the terminal constraint is always achievable for the control horizon and slack variables are not needed, which leads to a single decision variable for the optimization problem, $\Delta \mathbf{u}_k$. Also, assume that the system has no delays. The optimization problem

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for the IHMPCFF is summarized in the quadratic form as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
J_k = & \left\| \overline{\mathbf{A}}\mathbf{x}(k) + \overline{\mathbf{B}}\Delta\mathbf{u}_k + \overline{\mathbf{D}}\Delta\mathbf{d}_k - \mathbf{y}_{sp} \right\|_{\mathbf{Q}_y}^2 + \left\| (\mathbf{F})^m \mathbf{x}^{st}(k) + \overline{\mathbf{B}}_0^s \Delta\mathbf{u}_k \right\|_{\overline{\mathbf{Q}}}^2 + \\
& \left\| (\mathbf{F}^d)^m \mathbf{x}^d(k) + \overline{\mathbf{B}}_0^s \Delta\mathbf{d}_k \right\|_{\overline{\mathbf{Q}}_d}^2 + \left\| \Delta\mathbf{u}_k \right\|_{\mathbf{R}}^2
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Matrices $\overline{\mathbf{A}}$, $\overline{\mathbf{B}}$ and $\overline{\mathbf{D}}$ are related to the evolution of the system until the control horizon, wherein $\overline{\mathbf{A}}$ is the free-response dynamic matrix, $\overline{\mathbf{B}}$ is the matrix associated to the inputs moves and $\overline{\mathbf{D}}$ is the matrix associated to the disturbance measurements. Matrices $\overline{\mathbf{B}}_0^s$ and $\overline{\mathbf{B}}_0^d$ are the repeated values of \mathbf{B}_0^s and \mathbf{B}_0^d respectively, and vector $\Delta\mathbf{d}_k$ is defined as:

$$\Delta\mathbf{d}_k = [\Delta\mathbf{d}(k|k)^\top \ \Delta\mathbf{d}(k+1|k)^\top \ \dots \ \Delta\mathbf{d}(k+m-1|k)^\top]^\top$$

The control law can be obtained by minimizing Eq. (12) with respect to $\Delta\mathbf{u}_k$, whose solution can be provided analytically. For a initial steady-state system with reference $y_{sp} = 0$, the optimal $\Delta\mathbf{u}_k$ value is calculated as:

$$\Delta\mathbf{u}_k^* = \left(\overline{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{Q}_y \overline{\mathbf{B}} + \overline{\mathbf{B}}_0^s{}^\top \overline{\mathbf{Q}} \overline{\mathbf{B}}_0^s + \mathbf{R} \right)^{-1} \left(-\overline{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{Q}_y \overline{\mathbf{D}} \Delta\mathbf{d}_k \right) \tag{13}$$

From Eq. (13), it can be noted that, due to the terminal cost $\overline{\mathbf{Q}}$ arising from the infinity horizon formulation, even with no weighting for the input moves, the optimal input increments will never be able to perform like an external feedforward compensator. This situation only transpires when $\overline{\mathbf{Q}} = \mathbf{0}$ and $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{0}$, which will lead to the perfect compensation resulting from the division of the dynamic between the control inputs and the system outputs and the dynamics of the disturbances and the system's outputs:

$$\Delta\mathbf{u}_k^* = \left(\overline{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{Q}_y \overline{\mathbf{B}} \right)^{-1} \left(-\overline{\mathbf{B}}^\top \mathbf{Q}_y \overline{\mathbf{D}} \Delta\mathbf{d}_k \right)$$

Nevertheless, examining a numerical case, if the perfect rejection is desired, the control design must consider increasing the order of magnitude for the predicted output error penalty matrix, and the classical feedforward compensator

effect is approximately achieved. Notice that by increasing considerably the values of \mathbf{Q}_y in comparison to $\overline{\mathbf{Q}}$ and \mathbf{R} , $\Delta \mathbf{u}_k^*$ is computed as a classical feedforward structure. To put on prove the proposed analysis, consider the following example system:

$$G(s) = \frac{y(s)}{u(s)} = \frac{1}{s+1}e^{-1s}, \quad Gd(s) = \frac{y(s)}{d(s)} = \frac{1}{s+1}e^{-3s}$$

285 The system is simulated using four different control strategies: (i) the IHMPC with no feedforward compensation, (ii) the IHMPC+FF, (iii) the IHMPCFF with the $\mathbf{Q}_y = \text{diag}(1)$, and (iv) the IHMPCFF with $\mathbf{Q}_y = \text{diag}(10^3)$ (which is equivalent to have $\overline{\mathbf{Q}} = \mathbf{R} = \mathbf{0}$ in Eq. (13))¹. For all controllers, the same tuning is employed, which is: $m = 8$, $\mathbf{R} = \text{diag}(1)$, a sampling time $T_s = 1$,
 290 and $\mathbf{S}_y = 10^6$ and the reference is set in zero. Figure 1 depicts the simulation for the first scenario. As can be noted, the IHMPC with no feedforward action struggles to reject the effect of the disturbance. On the other hand, when the IHMPC+FF is applied, perfect compensation occurs, and the system output is not affected by the disturbance. However, the IHMPCFF with the implicit
 295 feedforward action can also perfectly reject the disturbance when the proper tuning is applied, that is, when \mathbf{Q}_y present higher magnitudes compared to $\overline{\mathbf{Q}}$ and \mathbf{R} .

3.2. Causality issues analysis

Although the IHMPF+FF rejects the disturbance effects, the classical feed-
 300 forward faces complexities in dealing with systems with input delays higher than the disturbance delays, which leads to non-causal dynamics of the feedforward structure. Therefore, as stated in Section 1, predictive controllers stand out as an attractive solution for this type of matter. In order to evaluate the non-causal issue of the stable IHMPCFF, consider the following example system:

¹For the sake of simplicity, in the course of this work, consider that the matrix dimension is correspondent to the system input, output and disturbances dimensions, in which $\mathbf{Q}_y \in \mathbb{R}^{ny \cdot m \times ny \cdot m}$, $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{nu \cdot m \times nu \cdot m}$, $\mathbf{S}_y \in \mathbb{R}^{ny \times ny}$

Figure 1: IHMPCFF feedforward analysis for control tuning with perfect disturbance compensation.

$$G(s) = \frac{y(s)}{u(s)} = \frac{1}{s+1}e^{-5s}, \quad Gd(s) = \frac{y(s)}{d(s)} = \frac{1}{s+1}e^{-3s}$$

305 In this stage, three controllers are proposed: (i) the IHMPC+FF (external feedforward), (ii) the IHMPCFF with no disturbance prediction, and (iii) the IHMPCFF with disturbance prediction. Figure 2 depicts the closed-loop system evolution for a step disturbance. The control tuning applied for all controllers is: $m = 8$, $\mathbf{Q}_y = \text{diag}(10^3)$, $T_s = 1$, $\mathbf{R} = \text{diag}(1)$ and $\mathbf{S}_y = 10^6$. For the
 310 external feedforward, only the causal part of the structure is implemented, as typically employed in industrial applications. As can be noted, regarding a non-causal structure, future information about the disturbance is necessary for the feedforward compensator. Even with the implicit feedforward action, if only the past measurements are used, the disturbance rejection action will deteriorate,
 315 as observed in Figure 2. Therefore, when disturbances predictions are available, the disturbance effect is completely removed thanks to the predictive capacities of the IHMPCFF.

Remark 3. *Suppose the disturbance prediction is known. In that case, the cost function decreasing property is not assured since the control optimization*

Figure 3: IHMPCFF feedforward analysis for input move restrictions.

As can be observed, both strategies can reject the disturbance effect until the sinusoidal amplitude increases, causing the input moves to achieve their maximum and minimum values. However, because the restriction limits are incorporated into the implicit feedforward action, the IHMPCFF can perform better than the IHMPC+FF. For quantitative analysis, the mean error-index is proposed, wherein its values is calculated as the mean of the difference between the output and its reference throughout the simulation. The IHMPC+FF presents the error-index of 0.282 and the IHMPCFF 0.270. The IHMPCFF can deal with the feedback and the feedforward circumstances in a single optimization problem, and thus it can provide optimal input movements considering its saturation. On the other hand, the IHMPC+FF strategy calculates the signal differently for the feedback and the feedforward situations, which can cause more significant oscillations since the input saturations are performed outside the optimization problem and are imposed abruptly to the input signal.

Accordingly, based on the previous analysis, the proposed nominal stabilizing IHMPCFF makes noticeable progress from the classical IHMPC. The proposed strategy can adequately compensate for the disturbances' effects, even though the terminal cost penalty arises due to the infinity horizon formulation. Fur-

thermore, the stable IHMPCFF stands out for circumventing the most common problems the external feedforward compensator faces, such as non-causal issues and input constraints, keeping the closed-loop stability properties.

4. Case study: Solar collector field control

Following the previous results, the IHMPCFF is implemented in a trustworthy simulated case study in order to control a solar collector field system. The controller study investigates the main practical implementation issues for the proposed stabilizing predictive controller regarding sampling time, nominal modeling, control horizon, optimization processing time, and, in addition, disturbance rejection.

Solar collector fields are mainly known as multi-disturbed systems with unpredictable and intermittent energy sources. The irradiance, which is the primary energy source, is measured but not manipulated, and the nature of the system disturbances significantly affects plant production. These features motivate the design of control strategies that can deal with these kinds of disturbances. Moreover, although the solar collector plants are open-loop stable systems and the disturbances are limited, a control design that guarantees closed-loop stability independently from its parameter tuning brings significant contributions to improving the plant performance. Therefore, the presented stable IHMPCFF emerges as an appealing and novel alternative for controlling the solar collector field. Nevertheless, the applicability of such a strategy must consider essential aspects regarding sampling time, computational processing time, and nominal models.

Therefore, a case study is presented based on an actual and validated solar thermal plant located at CIESOL center (in the University of Almería, Spain). Specifically, three main particularities of the system are studied:

- the validated system model is formulated in a nonlinear lumped-parameter differential equation fashion. Since the proposed IHMPCFF formulation is based on a nominal case, the operating point of the plant must be

investigated to provide a linear model that can represent the system in
 385 that plant condition;

- the controller sampling time election is a critical concern for the IHMPCFF formulation. Choosing a shorter sampling time makes the assumption of disturbances variations zero along the control horizon even more feasible, mainly when slow dynamic variables are considered, such as temperature, which corroborates with the proof of the IHMPCFF stability **Theorem**
 390 **2.1**;
- on the other hand, choosing shorter sampling times implies bigger controller matrices since the control horizon will increase to reach the system time constant.

395 4.1. Solar collector field model analysis

The studied solar collector system is formulated as a simplified lumped-parameter dynamical model, as depicted in [49, 52]:

$$\rho \cdot C_p \cdot A_{sc} \cdot \frac{dT_{sc,o}(t)}{dt} = \beta \cdot I(t) - \frac{H}{L} \cdot (T_{sc,m}(t) - T_a(t)) - \rho \cdot C_p \cdot \frac{q(t)}{c_f} \cdot \frac{T_{sc,o}(t) - T_{sc,in}(t - d_{in})}{L} \quad (14)$$

wherein ρ is the water density, C_p is the specific heat capacity of water, A_{sc} is the solar collector pipe cross-section area, $T_{sc,o}(t)$ and $T_{sc,in}(t)$ are the outlet and inlet temperature of the solar collector field, respectively, β is the irradiance model parameter, $I(t)$ and $T_a(t)$ are the solar irradiance and ambient temperature respectively, and H is the global losses coefficient. $T_{sc,m}(t)$ is the mean between the inlet and outlet temperature, that is $T_{sc,m}(t) = (T_{sc,o}(t) + T_{sc,in}(t))/2$. Then, L is the equivalent absorber tube length considering an equivalent flow $q(t)$, and
 400 c_f is the conversion factor to account for connections, number of modules and
 405 m^3/s conversion. Notice that the system has a delay time d_{in} associated with the inlet temperature, in which for this proposed study is considered constant as 50 s based on experimental identification results. It worths stressing that for this system the manipulated variable is the water flow $q(t)$ [m^3/h], the controlled

410 variable is the system output temperature $T_{sc,o}(t)$ [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] and the system disturbances are the inlet temperature $T_{sc,in}(t)$ [$^{\circ}\text{C}$], the ambient temperature $T_a(t)$ [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] and the solar irradiance $I(t)$ [W/m^2]. The parameter values are depicted in Table 2.

Table 2: Model parameters description for the solar collector field

Parameter	Unit
A_{sc}	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-4}$ [m^2]
c_f	$10 \cdot 3600$ [s/h]
C_p	4018 [$\text{J}/(\text{kg} \cdot ^{\circ}\text{C})$]
H	79.17 [$\text{J}/(\text{s} \cdot ^{\circ}\text{C})$]
L	46.6 [m]
β	0.432 [m]
ρ	1000 [kg/m^3]

Aiming to formulate the IHMPCFF controller, Eq. (14) must be linearized
 415 regarding the term $q(t) \cdot (T_{sc,o}(t) - T_{sc,in}(t - d_{in}))$. For this, the linear approximation using the Taylor series expansions truncated in the first derivative is used, resulting in the following linear differential equation:²

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underbrace{\frac{\rho C_p A_{sc}}{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} + \frac{H}{2L} \right]}}_{\tau} \frac{d\tilde{T}_{sc,o}(t)}{dt} + \tilde{T}_{sc,o}(t) &= \underbrace{\frac{-\frac{C_p \rho}{c_f L} (\bar{T}_{sc,o} - \bar{T}_{sc,i})}{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} + \frac{H}{2L} \right]}}_{K_q} \tilde{q}(t) + \underbrace{\frac{\beta}{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} + \frac{H}{2L} \right]}}_{K_I} \tilde{I}(t) + \\
 \underbrace{\frac{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} - \frac{H}{2L} \right]}{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} + \frac{H}{2L} \right]}}_{K_{T_{in}}} \tilde{T}_{in}(t) + \underbrace{\frac{\frac{H}{L}}{\left[\frac{\rho C_p \bar{q}}{c_f L} + \frac{H}{2L} \right]}}_{K_{T_a}} \tilde{T}_a(t) & \quad (15)
 \end{aligned}$$

As can be noted, the time constant and the input gains are dependent on the water flow operating point, \bar{q} , and the K_q gain is also dependent on the inlet-outlet temperature difference $\bar{T}_{sc,o} - \bar{T}_{sc,i}$. This dependence is analyzed over
 420

²The notation $\bar{\mathbb{X}}$ refers to the value of the variable at the selected equilibrium point, and $\tilde{\mathbb{X}}$ refers to the deviation variable around the equilibrium point.

the operation conditions of the CIESOL plant, wherein the water flow varies from 3 m³/h to 15 m³/h and the inlet-outlet temperature difference from 1 °C to 14 °C. Figures 4 and 5 shows the model parameters variation considering the different combination of the plant equilibrium point.

Figure 4: Linear model parameters analysis for $\tau(\bar{q})$, $K_I(\bar{q})$, $K_{T_a}(\bar{q})$ and $K_{T_{in}}(\bar{q})$

Figure 5: Linear model parameters analysis for $K_q(\bar{q}, \bar{T}_{sc,o}, \bar{T}_{sc,in})$, in which $\Delta T = \bar{T}_{sc,o} - \bar{T}_{sc,i}$

430 tigated based on the following ratio $|\mathbb{X}_{max} - \mathbb{X}_{min}| / |\mathbb{X}_{min}|$. For $\tau(\bar{q})$, $K_I(\bar{q})$ and $K_{T_a}(\bar{q})$, since only the denominator of the parameter terms is dependent on the water flow, it leads to the direct result of 3.577 maximum variation. On the other hand, for $K_q(\bar{q}, \bar{T}_{sc,o}, \bar{T}_{sc,in})$ and $K_{T_{in}}(\bar{q})$, the maximum parameter variation are 63.080 and 0.210, respectively. As demonstrated, the different equilibrium points of the nonlinear model can change the linearized model parameters, which can compromise the nominal property for the IHMPCFF.

435 Consequently, in order to maintain the linear model consistently representative for each operating point, the IHMPCFF application for the solar collector field considers updating the model parameters of the internal controller model at each sampling time, which results in an adaptive controller based on online linearization procedure. For that reason, in what follows, the dependence of the model parameters is referred to $q(t)$ and not to \bar{q} , as the operating point is changing. This proposed method requires special attention: since the internal model is updated constantly, the IHMPCFF controller must recalculate all matrices to develop the optimization problem formulated in Section 2, which requires additional computational time for computing the optimal inputs moves. Therefore, considering this subject and the previously mentioned trade-off between the control horizon and the disturbances variations assumption, the controller sampling time is investigated for the solar collector field implementation.
 440

4.2. IHMPCFF sampling time for the solar collector field

Consider the time constant $\tau(q(t))$ in Figure 4, wherein the minimum value is $\tau(q_{max}) = 12.4$ s and the maximum value is $\tau(q_{min}) = 51.6$ s. The analysis must consider that the sampling time must be small enough to comprise the smaller time constant and the prediction horizon must be large enough to predict the system outputs until $4 \cdot \tau$ unit of time ³. Nevertheless, the IHMPCFF matrices
 450

³This assumption is based on the first-order function of the linearized model, which is $y(t) = y_{ss} \cdot (1 - e^{-t/\tau})$. The settling time is reached in approximately $t = 4 \cdot \tau$, which leads to $y(4 \cdot \tau) = y_{ss} \cdot (1 - e^{-4 \cdot \tau/\tau}) = y_{ss} \cdot 0.9817$.

are calculated based on the control horizon, in which a shorter sampling time leads to a higher control horizon and, hence, increases the size of the controller's matrices. Moreover, the IHMPCFF matrices are directly dependent on the system time delays, that is, the longer the delays, the greater the number of states and the larger the size of the arrays. The purpose is to find the best sampling time value that meets the compromise between the control horizon and the computational processing time required to solve the optimization problem within one sampling time.

In order to find the proper sampling time for the proposed IHMPCFF implementation, an experimental scenario is simulated for controlling the solar collector field system. The simulations were performed in MATLAB[®] R2019b from Mathworks, using an Intel Core i7-7700 CPU 3.6 GHz, 16GB RAM computer. The IHMPCFF controller is simulated during a one-day campaign using real plant data. Table 3 depicts the simulation results for different sampling times and control horizon. The maximum prediction value is calculated for $4 \cdot \tau_{max} = 4 \cdot 50 = 200$ s.

Table 3: Sampling time and computational cost trade-off. T_{proc} is the mean processing time for each controller calculation during the simulation and $T_{procmax}$ is the maximum processing time achieved in a single controller calculations.

T_s [s]	m	T_{proc} [s]	$T_{procmax}$ [s]
1	200	1.802	2.413
2	100	0.568	0.991
5	40	0.250	0.448
10	20	0.201	0.436

As can be observed, the control sampling time $T_s = 1$ is not realizable in the software/hardware used since the control algorithm takes about 1.8 seconds to provide the optimal solution. However, when $T_s = 2$ s is employed, the IHMPCFF can perform the computations in half of the proposed sampling time for the worst-case scenario, $T_{procmax} = 0.991$.

Remark 4. Examining the proposed solar collector field scenario, as presented in Section 2, choosing smaller sampling times for the IHMPCFF controller corroborates with the assumption that $\Delta \mathbf{d}(k+m|k) = \mathbf{0}$, since the disturbances variables, mainly the inlet and ambient temperature, presents smooth dynamics and slow variations in short time intervals, such as $T_s = 2$ s. Moreover, for solar systems control, the assumption of keeping the disturbances variables constant along the prediction horizon is a common choice and widely applied in practice [3, 49].

4.3. IHMPCFF state estimation

Although the online linearization method is proposed, the IHMPCFF requires a state feedback framework for computing the future output predictions using the described model in Section 2, since the majority of the model states are not measured, that is $\mathbf{x}^s(k)$, $\mathbf{x}^{st}(k)$, $\mathbf{x}^d(k)$, $\mathbf{z}_l(k)$ and $\mathbf{z}_p^d(k)$. For this, a Kalman Filter-based state estimator is considered [56].

Figure 6 demonstrates the simulation results for the proposed model linearization method using the validated nonlinear model of the CIESOL solar collector field. The data is obtained from the actual plant operation on January 15, 2021. Simulation tests led to the robust response of the state estimator, in which the employed process noise covariance is $Q_{KF} = 10^{-2}$ and the measurement noise covariance is $R_{KF} = 10^{-3}$. The experiment confronts (i) the nonlinear model (Eq. (14)), (ii) the OPOM model obtained offline from the nonlinear model, (iii) the OPOM model linearized online, and (iv) the OPOM model linearized online with the Kalman filter. The chosen operating point for the offline linearization procedure is the beginning of the CIESOL operation in winter mode, which is: $\bar{q} = 6.94$ m³/h, $\bar{T}_{sc,in} = 41.88$ °C, $\bar{I} = 265.85$ W/m², $\bar{T}_a = 13.07$ °C and $\bar{T}_{sc,o} = 45.65$ °C.

In this mismatch simulation scenario, the real plant is considered as the nonlinear model for means of comparison. The mean-error index calculated by the difference between the nonlinear model and the linear models is detailed in Table 4. As can be observed from Figure 6, the linear model error is higher

when the plant operates with low water flow, approximately $3 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. However, the online linearization procedure can readjust the model parameters in each operating point and, consequently, improve the curve adjustment compared to the offline procedure. In addition, the employment of the Kalman filter, apart from providing the model state's estimation, also improves the linear model fitting since the actual measurements of the plant's output are used to calculate the states.

Figure 6: Linear model validation

Table 4: Mean-error index for linear model analysis

Mean-error index [°C]		
OPOM - offline	OPOM - online	OPOM - online + KF
0.5018	0.4766	0.0659

A significant concern about implementing IHMPCFF to control the solar collector field must be mentioned. As observed, the nominal condition for the nonlinear system is achieved by employing the online linearization and the state estimation method. Suppose the system has extensive delay time and extra inputs, outputs, and disturbances. In that case, the number of states of the OPOM model increases considerably, reflecting on the complexity of the pre-

diction model matrices and, hence, the processing time required for calculating the linear model and estimating its states. Although feasibility is achieved with small control horizons due to the IHMPCFF formulation in Section 2, i.e., $m = 1$, control horizons that comprise the system dynamic are advised for solar systems control requirements. Therefore, investigating the control sampling time for implementing the strategy must be reinforced to meet the compromise of the trade-off between the control requirements (feasibility, nominal condition, control horizon, and process time constant) and computational cost.

Moreover, it is noteworthy that the convergence analysis presented in Section 2 is developed for Linear time-invariant (LTI) systems, and the proposed implementation of the IHMPCFF considers a linear time-varying scenario. Thus, the convergence analysis is unsuitable during the transient from one operating point to another. However, it holds when the system is kept in the current operating point as the linearization method, and the Kalman Filter framework can approximate the nonlinear model accurately to a linear one, and, hence, the nominal stability properties can be employed.

4.4. Simulation results

Supported by the previous analysis, this section presents the results of the proposed stable IHMPCFF applied for controlling the solar collector field. The controller is simulated for a five-day campaign using real plant data from March 27, 2021, to March 31, 2021. Although the CIESOL facility presents various subsystems, since the presented study concerns only the control analysis, the plant configuration is simplified, considering only the solar collector field and an exemplified load system, herein presented as a heat-exchanger. For the sake of representation, the simulated CIESOL facility is controlled based on an ON-OFF algorithm for the summer operating mode, in which the plant starts to operate when the irradiance achieves 300 W/m^2 and stops operating when the irradiance is low than 300 W/m^2 for more than 10 min. In addition, the output temperature reference is established in $72 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is the required temperature for the load system in a real scenario. Figure 7 depicts the simulated CIESOL

plant configuration.

Figure 7: Condensed CIESOL facility solar plant

The IHMPCFF is compared with the classical IHMPC associated with the external feedforward compensator to study the control performance regarding disturbances rejection and robustness. Figure 8 details both applied control strategies, wherein the external feedforward structures G_{f_I} , $G_{f_{T_a}}$ and $G_{f_{T_{in}}}$ are imposed for the three disturbance variables for the IHMPC+FF case. Moreover, the heat exchanger variables are $T_{he,h,in}(t)$, the inlet temperature of the hot side, $T_{he,h,o}(t)$ the outlet temperature of the hot side, $T_{he,c,in}(t)$ the inlet temperature of the cold side, $T_{he,c,o}(t)$, the inlet temperature of the cold side and $q_c(t)$ the water flow of the cold side. It is important to stress that the linear model described in Eq. (15) presents a single time constant for the four inputs variables, including one manipulated variable ($q(t)$) and the three disturbance variables ($I(t)$, $T_a(t)$, $T_{sc,in}(t)$). Therefore, the external feedforward

compensator development does not consider the system dynamics but only the
 560 input-output gains. Consequently, based on the proposed linearization procedure, the feedforward structures G_{f_I} , $G_{f_{T_a}}$ and $G_{f_{T_{in}}}$ are also updated to adjust the disturbance gains to the current system's operating point.

Figure 8: (A) IHMPCFF and (B) IHMPC+FF control schemes for a discrete time simulation

The stabilizing predictive controllers are simulated considering the following
 control tuning: $T_s = 2$ s, $m = 100$, $\mathbf{Q}_y = \text{diag}(10)$, $T_s = 1$, $\mathbf{R} = \text{diag}(20)$ and
 565 $\mathbf{S}_y = \text{diag}(10^6)$. The input limits are imposed as $u_{min} = 3$, $u_{max} = 15$ and
 $\Delta u_{max} = -\Delta u_{min} = 1.02$ m³/h, corresponding to the actual operation limits
 of the CIESOL facility. The Kalman Filter-based state estimator is tuned as
 presented in Section 4.3. Figure 9 displays the simulation curves only for the
 IHMPCFF. The IHMPC+FF has also been implemented considering the same
 570 scenario conditions, however, with the purpose to provide clarity results, the
 controller curve responses were omitted. In addition, Figure 10 presents the
 load system operation.

As can be noted, when methodological conditions are insufficient, the con-

Figure 9: IHMPCFF simulation results for the CIESOL facility operation

Figure 10: CIESOL heat exchanger input variables

575 control inputs saturate, and consequently, the temperature deviates from the refer-
 ence. Nevertheless, in the case of sufficient conditions, the IHMPCFF and the
 IHMPC+FF can adequately control the solar collector field and guide the out-
 put temperature variable to the reference despite the effects of the disturbances.
 In order to compare the IHMPCFF with the implicit feedforward action and
 the IHMPC+FF with the external disturbance compensator, Figure 11 displays

580 the temperature control for the operating conditions of day 1. Moreover, the mean-error index and the integral of the absolute error (IAE) are calculated for the operating point in each day, considering only when there are sufficient conditions to achieve the temperature reference, that is: Day 1 [11 - 14 h], Day 2 [10.5 - 14 h], Day 3 [10 - 14.5 h], Day 4 [11 - 13.5 h] and Day 5 [10.5 - 14.5h].
 585 The indices are presented in Table 5.

Figure 11: Temperature control on operating conditions for the IHMPCFF and IHMPC+FF on day-1

Table 5: Error indices analysis for IHMPCFF and IHMPC+FF

	IHMPCFF		IHMPC+FF	
	Mean-error [°C]	IAE [°C]	Mean-error [°C]	IAE [°C]
Day 1	0.4153	2243.10	0.7408	4001.00
Day 2	0.0633	398.60	0.3618	2279.60
Day 3	0.3673	2975.20	0.6795	5504.90
Day 4	0.6018	2708.70	1.1077	4985.90
Day 5	0.4907	3533.20	0.5051	5939.20
Total	0.3764	11858.80	0.8248	22710.60

As observed from the previous results, both controllers can accurately reg-

ulate the solar plant, with a performance improvement for the IHMPCFF. It is worth stressing that due to the proposed sampling time and the Kalman filter-based state estimator, the disturbance compensations are well employed for both stable predictive controllers, either with the implicit or external feedforward compensation. However, as can be observed in Figure 11, the IHMPCFF has a more aggressive response than the IHMPC+FF when the same control tuning is applied. The IHMPCFF can provide a combined input response, considering the feedback and feedforward actions, which allows tuning both actions for the closed-loop response. On the other hand, the proposed IHMPC+FF considers only the feedback action control tuning, and, hence, this single tuning compromises the closed-loop performance, which requires further analysis to design improved control parameters tuning [2].

The formulation differences between the two controllers require attention. As investigated in Section 3, the external feedforward framework can present difficulties concerning non-causal dynamics and input or output constraints, which can compromise the performance of the IHMPC+FF. Moreover, although the investigated nonlinear solar collector field presents only an input-output feedforward gain structure, in which becomes simpler to readjust the external feedforward block when applying the online linearization method, in case different dynamics arise from the nonlinear model, the adjustment of the feedforward structure is not trivial, making the adaptive algorithm more elaborated. Hence, straightened by the stability properties, the incorporated disturbance compensation, and the demonstrated practical applicability features, the proposed IHMPCFF stands out as an attractive strategy to circumvent the mentioned issues.

5. Conclusion

This paper presents a closed-loop stabilizing model predictive control with implicit feedforward action for stable and time-delayed systems. The proposed control strategy has guaranteed nominal stability by demonstrating that the cost function obeys the Lyapunov stability properties for the closed-loop system.

The applicability of the proposed stable predictive strategy is tested in a case study scenario for controlling a solar collector field system.

The principal considerations of this study can be highlighted in two domains, theoretical and practical. Considering the first one, as investigated in Section 3, the IHMPCFF presents remarkable properties in contrast to the classical feed-
620 forward compensator. Although the IHMPCFF control law does not guarantee the perfect cancellation of the disturbance dynamics due to terminal cost and the input effort weighting matrix, this result can be approximated by assuming large magnitudes of the output error weighting matrix. In addition, the
625 novel strategy can overcome the significant issues of the external feedforward structure, such as non-causal issues and variables constraints, besides assuring a closed-loop stability response. On the other hand, considering the practical point of view, the IHMPCFF has been successfully implemented for controlling a solar thermal system. Special attention regarding sampling time, control
630 horizon, and state estimation must be considered for this practical scenario, as demonstrated in Section 4. Nevertheless, the IHMPCFF can deal with these particularities and robustly control the proposed nonlinear system, accurately rejecting the disturbances and presenting an improved performance compared to the IHMPC with an external feedforward structure. As noted, IHMPCFF
635 obtained nearly 50% less error than IHMPC+FF in the reference tracking case when the same control tuning is applied. Moreover, the IHMPCFF presents a straightforward adjustment mechanism for guaranteeing stability and feedback and feedforward tuning, which is a tremendous advantage for the control system design. Such results favorably indicate that the presented stabilizing
640 control algorithm is implementable in real systems.

Finally, based on the achieved state of the art, the proposed IHMPCFF can also be extended for unstable, integrating, and multi-integrating systems and, in addition, comprise a robust stability formulation. Future works propose developing stability properties considering disturbance prediction to enhance the
645 control performance and robustness of the IHMPCFF by including disturbance forecasts along the control horizon.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Igor M. L. Pataro: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, review and editing, Visualization. **Juan D. Gil:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft, review and editing, Visualization **Marcus V. Americano da Costa:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization. **José L. Guzmán:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization. **Manuel Berenguel:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing - review, Visualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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